

Tourism: A Tool for Women Empowerment and Gender Equality in India

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is acts as an engine for growth by generating foreign exchange earnings and direct and indirect employment. The Draft Tourism Policy 1997 sees the emergence of tourism as a key tool for sustainable human development including poverty alleviation and employment generation. Empowerment is the most discussed issue in the present scenario in all spheres of human life. In most developing countries, gender inequality and discrimination are major obstacles to development. As many tourism studies have made an important connection between tourism, social development and women's empowerment, the UN has created an important political agenda to research and work on issues in this area.

Significant attention has been paid to the role of tourism in promoting gender equality, increasing women's employment and improving their incomes. Economic empowerment of women through tourism can be well gauged by the percentage share of female workforce in India's tourism sectors. The total percentage share of women workers in the tourism sector is 34, which is higher than the total percentage of women workers in other sectors. There is a lot of scope for empowering women in the tourism sector with very little investment. Tourism is vast scope for women empowerment in both formal and informal sectors of tourism.

Key Words: Tourism, Women empowerment, Women workers, Female workforce,

Introduction

Tourism is one of the largest and fastest growing industries in the world. In many countries it acts as an engine for growth by generating foreign exchange earnings and direct and indirect employment (WTO). Tourism contributes 5% of the world's GDP and 7% of global jobs. It accounts for 6% of world exports and 30% of world exports in services. In developing countries, tourism accounts for 45% of total exports of services (UNWTO). Research shows various ways in which tourism contributes to economic growth, poverty reduction and social development. The Draft Tourism Policy 1997 sees the emergence of tourism as a key tool for sustainable human development including poverty alleviation and employment generation. Environmental rehabilitation and advancement of women and other disadvantaged groups in India.

Summery

Tourism presents both opportunities and challenges for gender equality and women's empowerment. Women's participation in the business world has increased in recent years, although women are underrepresented in management and leadership. In the tourism sector, the percentage of women working in the industry is high, but their activity is dominated by unskilled, low-paid jobs. The tourism sector presents various entry points for women's employment, opportunities to create self-employment activities, small and gender-stereotyped employment and discrimination, where women tend to work mainly in cooking, cleaning and hospitality. Most tourism employment fluctuates seasonally and with the volatility of the industry. When a strong gender perspective is integrated into planning and implementation processes, tourism can be used as a vehicle to promote gender equality and women's empowerment at family, community, national and global levels. At the same time, greater gender equality will contribute to the overall quality of the tourism experience, with a significant impact on profitability and quality in all aspects of the industry. However, there are several conditions under which this ability can be used more effectively. This requires the cooperation of all stakeholders including governments and intergovernmental organizations, local governments, industry, trade unions, local communities and their various member groups, NGOs, community-based tourism

initiatives, etc. Increasing cultural heritage and social and economic justice should be the goal of further tourism development.

Empowerment is the most discussed issue in the present scenario in all spheres of human life. In most developing countries, gender inequality and discrimination are major obstacles to development. One of the most important aspects of achieving the Millennium Development Goals by 2015 is to try to eliminate the gap between women and men in terms of skills, access to resources and opportunities, and vulnerability to violence and conflict. One aspect where gender (inequality) issues can play an important role is tourism development¹. As many tourism studies have made an important connection between tourism, social development and women's empowerment, the UN has created an important political agenda to research and work on issues in this area. That is why UNWTO presented an Action Plan on Women's Empowerment through Tourism at the last IDP in Berlin. The action plan focuses on poverty reduction and improving the dignity and role of women in the workplace².

Empowerment is a broad dimension that includes the important aspect of gender equality in society, where men and women enjoy the same opportunities, outcomes, rights and obligations in every sphere of their daily work. In the throttling era of globalization, while the world is rapidly changing and progressing, rural women are worried about their dependent existence, a poor socioeconomic status that cripples future development.

UNWTO Secretary General Zurab Pololikashvili says:

“The restart of tourism must include everyone and the benefits must be enjoyed by all. Tourism has proven itself a true champion of gender equality and these new guidelines will help both governments and businesses harness the sector’s power as a driver of women’s empowerment as the world opens up again”.

After reviewing the academic literature on women's empowerment in tourism, it is also useful to look at its practical implications. During a conference in Berlin in March 2008, the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) implemented an action

plan for the empowerment of women through tourism³. The program's objectives derive from the United Nations Millennium Development Goals, which aim to empower the poor (including through tourism), protect the environment and empower women. Tourism is an important part of the world's GDP (more than 10%) and generates 8% of the world's employment. 60-70% of all people working in the tourism sector are women (UNWTO, 2008). There are large annual growth projections in aggregate demand in the coming years (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2008). It offers many opportunities to developed and developing countries in rural, urban, regional or cultural areas. Tourism growth can be a major catalyst for development and empowerment of women, which makes the WTO program a legitimate motivation to empower women through this sector. Despite many international agreements organized to value and promote women's rights, the UNFPA (United Nations Population Fund) says they are more likely to be poor, malnourished and illiterate than men. They generally have less access than men to health care, property rights, credit, training and employment. They are less likely than men to be politically active and more likely to be victims of domestic violence' (UNFPA, 2008). Thus women's empowerment can significantly contribute to achieving gender equality.

The UN defines empowerment as a critical aspect of gender equality, and defines both concepts as following (UNFPA, 2008):

‘Gender equality implies a society in which women and men enjoy the same opportunities, outcomes, rights and obligations in all spheres of life. Equality between men and women exists when both sexes are able to share equally in the distribution of power and influence; have equal opportunities for financial independence through work or through setting up businesses; enjoy equal access to education and the opportunity to develop personal ambitions. A critical aspect of promoting gender equality is the empowerment of women, with a focus on identifying and redressing power imbalances and giving women more autonomy to manage their own lives. Women's empowerment is vital to sustainable development and the realization of human rights for all.’

Since the enactment of the National Tourism Policy 2002, the government has implemented its five-year plans (eg, the Tenth Five-Year Plan, 2002-2007; the Eleventh Five-Year Plan, 2007-2012; and the Twelfth Five-Year Plan 2012-2017) and the Thirteenth Five-Year Plan (2017-2022).) has consistently reaffirmed the positioning of tourism as a national priority. Tourism is considered to offer better opportunities for promoting pro-poor development than many other sectors, as it can generate employment for a wide range of job seekers, from the unskilled to the skilled, in remote areas of the country. Also, the Approach Paper for the Twelfth Five Year Plan 2012-2017 estimates that women will have a higher proportion of tourism benefits (jobs, small business opportunities) compared to other modern sectors⁴. This underscores the potential of the tourism sector to realize direct and multiple impacts on women's economic development, including by creating spaces for women's participation in decision-making.

According to the Global Report on Women in Tourism, "If a gender perspective is integrated into planning and implementation processes, the sector offers great potential to promote GEWE at family, community, national and global levels"⁵. This report is the first report. An attempt to develop a quantitative framework for monitoring the status of women working in tourism worldwide.

The tourism industry is well positioned to promote social participation and improve the status of women in tourism. Primarily, the Ministry of Tourism in accordance with the Constitution of India, specifically Articles 15, 16, and 39 prohibits discrimination of any kind against women and promotes equal employment and equal pay for women and men. It is gender sensitive and its concerns include promoting equal rights of women⁶.

In this gender analysis, it is proposed to include "(i) an overview of women's involvement in tourism at all levels, (ii) the extent to which women are mobilized in self-help groups or other community social structures. Involvement, and (iii) an assessment of possible ways to support women in equitable access to skills development for paid employment or entrepreneurial activities in tourism that could result from the investment."⁷

Gender equality is the primary indicator of sustainable tourism, where the improvement of women's conditions leads to the improvement of tourism sustainability⁸. Apart from that, through the tourism sector, the status of women is achieving some positive development⁹. Significant attention has been paid to the role of tourism in promoting gender equality, increasing women's employment and improving their incomes. However, research and knowledge on gender equality is essential in tourism. The fifth goal for the SDGs related to women's empowerment, translated into a set of sub-goals that ensure gender equality. According to the Global Report on Women in Tourism, these sub-goals differ between employment, entrepreneurship, education and training, leadership and decision-making and participation in society and civil society. At the same time, 54% of women working in tourism are As mentioned, it has a higher representation than any other economic sector¹⁰.

Gender in tourism continues to be an important boundary topic in the sociological research of tourism. In general, tourism studies have discussed and popularized a gender perspective on gender equality since the 1980s. These initial studies focus on assessing gender sustainability in tourist destinations, and discuss gender differences in tourism perceptions at different development stages, power relations that contribute to gender differences¹¹.

In general, tourism studies have discussed and popularized a gender perspective on gender equality since the 1990s, which is considered a turning point in the gender and tourism literature. Two important scholarly literatures appeared during this period: *Tourism, A Gender Analysis* (1994), a book on the analysis of tourism studies in the United States and Europe, and other leading research is the *Annals of Tourism Research* Journal in 1995, *Gender in Tourism*¹². Also, Kinnard and Hall¹³ define three pillars. are essential to understanding the relationship between tourism and gender. The first pillar adopted in tourism activities is gender, built on complex and multifaceted social relations. The second pillar focused on the role of political, economic, cultural, social and environmental interactions in shaping gender relations. Finally the concept of equality

and inequality is built on the concept of diversity not only in gender but also in religion, age and class. These pillars have opened up the field for four main dimensions located in the field of tourism research; Gender tourism, the gendered host, gendered marketing and the gendered tourism landscape¹⁴.

In the 2000s, this field of research was developed through Gender Worker, Gender and Sex Tourism, and Gender and Sustainability¹⁵. International organizations have had a significant influence on current scholarly literature in framing the developmental trajectory of the relationship between gender and tourism. The United Nations (UN), the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the International Labor Organization (ILO) play a leading role in promoting awareness of gender equality in the tourism sector through three key documents: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development¹⁶, the Global Report of Women in Tourism¹⁷, and the International Perspectives on Women and Work in Hotels, Catering, and Tourism¹⁸ respectively. An International Perspective on Women and Work in Catering and Tourism”. This literature development trend indicates the interest not only from researchers but also from international organizations in the tourism sector from a gender perspective.

Percentage share of women's employment through tourism in most of the world's economies related to tourism Tourism's contribution to women's empowerment can be well determined. Table 1 shows the percentage share of employment of women in some World's leading tourism economy.

Table:1 Percentage share of women employment in Tourism Industry¹⁹

Sl.No	Country	Employment (%)
1	Australia	55.80
2	Canada	55.00
3	Dominican Republic	50.00
4	Mexico	47.00
5	Egypt	25.00

In Australia, the tourism industry has 55.8 percent female employment, which is relatively high compared to other tourism economies such as Canada—55 percent. Dominican Republic – 50 percent, Mexico – 47 percent and Egypt – 25 percent, whereas in India, women's contribution to the tourism sector is approximately 30 percent. Region-wise participation of women in hotel and restaurant industry is given in Table-2.

Table: 2 Percentage share of women employment in Hotel and Restaurant (%)²⁰

Sl.No	Country	Employment (%)
1	Latin Australia	58.50
2	Caribbean	55.40
3	Africa	47.00
4	Oceania	46.80
5	Asia	35.40

table-2 shows the participation of women in hotel and restaurant. Women's participation in the hotel and restaurant business averages 49 percent. It is highest in Latin America region with 58.5 percent and lowest in Asia with 35.4 percent. Above average female participation in tourism industry in India.

Empowerment of women through tourism is an important area of concern today. As such, tourism is one of the important sectors of India and provides livelihood to local people in and around various tourist destinations. It is the main means of income for all sections of the society, ie, skilled and unskilled, men and women. Therefore, it is one of the main sources of women empowerment.

Table: 3. Percentage share of employment in tourism in India²¹

Sl.No	Gender	Employment (%)
1	Male	66.00
2	Female	34.00
Total		100.00

According to a study on women empowerment through tourism in India, 34 percent of the women population is directly linked to the state's tourism sector (Table 3). Of the total direct employment through tourism, 34 per cent of the workforce are female as against 66 per cent of male employees, which is higher than the average percentage share of 30 per cent of the total female workforce in the state (Census 2001). In India, the tourism sector is contributing a lot to women's empowerment. They get equal opportunities in tourism and tourism related fields. Both skilled and unskilled women are actively involved in the tourism sector.

The Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated gender discrimination in global labor markets. Recent studies have highlighted that unemployment among women has increased; Women experienced more pay cuts than men; Women's childcare and housework responsibilities increased and with the Covid-19 outbreak women started working more from home. All these developments indicate that gender discrimination has increased globally. Also, some industries experience more gender discrimination, such as the health and tourism industries (WTTC. 2020a). The gender bias of Covid-19 in the tourism sector can be seen directly from the countries' tourism satellite accounts. The Tourism Satellite Account (TSA) is a standard statistical framework for measuring economic indicators in the tourism sector. From September 2019 to September 2020, tourism jobs have changed -10.2% for men and -15.49% for women. Thus, unemployment is more pronounced for women and hence gender discrimination in employment has increased. Over the same period, full-time job losses (-16.4%) outnumbered part-time job losses (-14.4%) across women, indicating that long-term employment opportunities remain for women. The United Nations Department of Women released a report and it underlined that the COVID-19 outbreak has increased gender discrimination globally. Immigrant women, women living below the poverty line, and women from disadvantaged ethnic groups are most affected, and these effects persist for a long time. Women working in informal jobs lost approximately 60% of their income even by the end of the first month of the epidemic. The ILO (2020a) underlines that in the Asia and Pacific region alone, 81 million jobs will be lost in 2020, 32 million of which will be women's jobs. Moreover, the rate of decline in female employment has been consistent with 4.6%, which is higher than the rate of decline in male employment of 4%

in this region²². Gender-based realities in tourism are very important as tourism is one of the main industries in the current world economy and gender discrimination is experienced even in this industry.

Conclusion

Tourism is one of the main sources of empowerment of women. In India, the tourism industry is playing a major role in empowering women. Women, both skilled and unskilled, are actively involved in the tourism sector and its decision-making in most high-tech and underdeveloped states. Economic empowerment of women through tourism can be well gauged by the percentage share of female workforce in India's tourism sectors. The total percentage share of women workers in the tourism sector is 34, which is higher than the total percentage of women workers in other sectors. Apart from direct employment through tourism, women are also indirectly involved in tourism-related activities such as hotels, restaurants, canteens, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), various home businesses, tea shops, travel, handloom and handicrafts. It occupies a significant position in various parts of the country. India has natural beauty and resources and hence, more potential in the tourism sector. With the arrival of more tourists, employment opportunities will also increase. Therefore, there is a lot of scope for empowering women in the tourism sector with very little investment. Tourism is a service-oriented, labour-intensive and multi-dimensional sector linked to many sectors of the economy such as transport, hotels, restaurants, travel and tourism businesses, seasonal housing etc. Hence, there is vast scope for women empowerment in both formal and informal sectors of tourism.

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